

Sneaking up on ‘enemies’: alleviating inherent disadvantages in competitive outcomes in a nearly 3-million-year-old palaeocommunity from Florida, USA

EMANUELA DI MARTINO , LEE HSIANG LIOW, TOM PERKINS, ROGER W. PORTELL AND PAUL D. TAYLOR

LETHAIA

Di Martino, E., Liow, L. H., Perkins, T., Portell, R. W., & Taylor, P. D. 2020: Sneaking up on ‘enemies’: alleviating inherent disadvantages in competitive outcomes in a nearly 3-million-year-old palaeocommunity from Florida, USA. *Lethaia*, Vol. 53, pp. 553–562.

Bryozoans offer one of the few systems in which competitive interactions for living space can be studied in the fossil record. Here, we describe the outcome of competitive overgrowths in a 3-million-year-old bryozoan palaeocommunity encrusting shells of the bivalve *Anomia simplex* from the lower Tamiami Formation in Florida (upper Pliocene, Piacenzian). We found that win–lose overgrowths are more common than stand-offs in interspecific encounters, while stand-offs are more common than win–lose overgrowths in intraspecific encounters. We observed more intraspecific encounters and fewer interspecific interactions than expected under a null hypothesis, suggesting that bryozoans of the same species are likely to be clustered. For some species, intraspecific encounters are more likely to result in the apparent fusion of the two colonies, with the development of rows of kenozooids along the contact edge, probably reflecting relatively low dispersal. We also identified some clear winners and some clear losers. A negative correlation was found between the number of colonies observed and the probability of winning for a species, resulting in a dominance of loser species in the assemblage, a pattern previously described as typical for early colonizers of hard substrates. Our results also confirm the finding of earlier studies that having large zooids and, subordinately, multilayered growth are key traits for success in overgrowth competition, with angle of encounter also having an effect for both poor and good competitors that take advantage of ‘attacking’ colonies of other species from the rear and the flank. □ *Bryozoa*, *Cheilostomata*, *ecological interactions*, *overgrowths*, *spatial competition*.

Emanuela Di Martino [e.d.martino@nhm.uio.no], and Lee Hsiang Liow [l.h.liow@ibv.uio.no], Natural History Museum, University of Oslo, Blindern, P.O. Box 1172 Oslo 0318, Norway; Lee Hsiang Liow [l.h.liow@ibv.uio.no], Centre for Ecological and Evolutionary Synthesis, Department of Biosciences, University of Oslo, Blindern, P.O. Box 1066, Oslo 0316, Norway; Tom Perkins [tomp7643@gmail.com], Department of Earth Sciences, Natural History Museum, Cromwell Road, London SW7 5BD, UK; Roger W. Portell [portell@flmnh.ufl.edu], Division of Invertebrate Paleontology, Florida Museum of Natural History, University of Florida, Gainesville, FL32611, USA; Paul D. Taylor [p.taylor@nhm.ac.uk], Departments of Earth and Life Sciences, Natural History Museum, Cromwell Road, London SW7 5BD, UK; manuscript received on 10/10/2019; manuscript accepted on 17/01/2020.

As the majority of bryozoans live as sessile encrusters of hard substrates such as rocks and shells, substrate availability is a prime factor controlling their distribution (Taylor 2016). After the larva settles on the substrate, the colony begins to develop and expand in size, often leading to competition for living space with other epibionts. These competitive interactions can be preserved in the fossil record because of the calcified skeletons of the taxa involved, offering one of the few systems in which to study directly competition in the geological past.

Studies on competition using fossil bryozoans are, however, limited: some have been conducted at inter-clade level (i.e. Cyclostomata vs. Cheilostomata), and others involve small sample sizes (Taylor 2016, and

references therein). Only recently, an extensive study was conducted using bryozoan-encrusted mollusc shells from the Pleistocene of the Wanganui Basin in New Zealand (Liow *et al.* 2016, 2017, 2019). Tracking species-specific competition through 2 million years, these studies have demonstrated that some species are consistent winners or consistent losers in spatial competition (Liow *et al.* 2016), that relatively larger zooid size is a determinant factor to succeed in overgrowths (Liow *et al.* 2017), and that the effect of this zooid-size advantage changes over time and there is considerable stochasticity in overgrowth outcomes given a species pair (Liow *et al.* 2019).

Here, we describe 3-million-year-old competitive outcomes from an *Anomia*-associated bryozoan

palaeocommunity to add to the currently sparse existing literature on competition ‘frozen in time’. Although limited to a single time-slice, this material is especially suitable for studying competition: abundant encrusted shells were available, the monospecific nature of the substrate collected from the same facies minimizes environmental differences, the taxonomy of the bryozoan competitors is well-known (see Di Martino *et al.* 2019), and the observation of only a few examples of fouling and a high proportion of intraspecific encounters resulting in stand-offs provides good evidence for syn-vivo interactions as opposed to post-mortem overgrowths (Taylor 2016). Using this palaeocommunity, we: (1) corroborate previous findings that both a module-level trait – relative size of feeding zooids – and a colony-level trait – multilayered growth – determine species-level competitive outcomes; (2) quantitatively test whether the encounter angle, an interaction-level feature, can promote competitive success in otherwise poor competitors; (3) investigate how commonly intraspecific encounters result in apparent fusion between colonies; and (4) discuss the similarity/dissimilarity of the competitive advantages of species within a genus, and its implications for palaeoecological studies.

Material and methods

Material used for this study was collected from Units 10/11 of the upper Pliocene (Piacenzian) lower Tami-ami Formation exposed in Phase 10 excavations (now water-filled) of the SMR Aggregates quarries, situated northeast of Sarasota, Florida (27.373907°, –82.376859°; WGS84) (Fig. 1), during July 2017. To minimize environmental differences, we targeted only bryozoan-encrusted left valves of the bivalve *Anomia simplex* d’Orbigny, estimated as dating from 3.0 ± 0.5 Ma (Jones *et al.* 1991). Before examining the encrusting bryozoan colonies, the 867 shell substrates were gently cleaned under running water, scrubbed with a soft toothbrush, washed in an ultrasonic bath to remove sediment, and air-dried. Shell areal coverage was visually estimated from pictures. Bryozoan colonies were identified to species level using a stereomicroscope. Taxonomic identification was confirmed using a low-vacuum scanning electron microscope (LEO VP-1455) on selected specimens at the Natural History Museum in London (NHMUK).

A limited number of interactions was observed between bryozoans and other epibionts (i.e. corals, barnacles, foraminifera and spirorbid polychaetes; Fig. 2; Table 1), while a large number of interactions,

Fig. 1. Map of Florida with the star indicating the location of the sampling site in Sarasota County (modified from Di Martino *et al.* 2019). [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

both intra- and interspecific, were observed between bryozoan colonies (Fig. 3; Tables 2–4). The presence of epibionts other than bryozoans was tabulated only when interacting with a bryozoan colony. All interactions were recorded following the standard protocol of Liow *et al.* (2016, 2017, 2019): each shell, colony and interaction was assigned a unique number in the database; interactions were classified as follows: (1) win–lose overgrowths (the growing edge of the winner colony elevates and covers orifices of zooids in the losing colony); (2) reciprocal overgrowths (both colonies mutually cover each other); (3) stand-offs (the two colonies abut without overgrowth at the encounter edge); or (4) fouling (one colony settled on top of another). Relative zooid size at the interacting edges was visually estimated with respect to ‘Colony_1’ for each win–lose interaction as larger, smaller or equal. Presence or absence of multilayered growth was tabulated for each colony in a competing pair. In addition, following Jackson (1979, p. 814, fig. 4), the encounter angle, defined as the angle between the direction of growth of the overgrown colony and the overgrowing colony, was visually estimated for each interaction colony, was visually estimated for each interaction again with respect to ‘Colony_1’ and classified according to three broad categories: (1) frontal, that is opposing growth directions (c. 120–180°); (2) flank, that is directions of growth perpendicular (60–120°); and (3) rear, that is same directions of growth (c. 0–60°). In frontal encounters, the contact between the two colonies occurs growing

Fig. 2. Scanning electron micrographs (SEM) of overgrowth interactions between bryozoan colonies and other organisms. A, *Floridina regularis* partly overgrowing a tube of a spirorbid (Shell 24, UF 305772). B, *Metroperiella reversa* partly overgrowing a barnacle (arrowed) (Shell 3, UF 305779). C, *Amphiblestrum constrictum* (lower left) overgrown by the coral *Astrangia* (upper right) (Shell 27, UF 305805).

Table 1. Summary of the competitive outcomes between bryozoan species and other epibionts.

Species	Barnacles				Corals				Foraminifera				Spirorbirds			
	W	L	SO	R	W	L	SO	R	W	L	SO	R	W	L	SO	R
<i>Amphiblestrum constrictum</i>	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0					1	0	0	0
<i>Aplousina grandis</i>	3	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	3	0	0	0				
<i>Celleporaria</i> sp.	2	0	0	0												
<i>Copidozoum</i> cf. <i>parvirostris</i>																
<i>Cyclocolpoda perforata</i>	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0				
<i>Cycloperiella rubra</i>	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0				
<i>Floridina regularis</i>	5	0	0	0	3	1	2	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	1	0
<i>Hippopleurifera mucronata</i>	1	0	0	0												
<i>Metroperiella reversa</i>	4	0	0	0	2	0	0	0								
<i>Microporella</i> cf. <i>pontifica</i>	7	4	0	0	6	2	0	0	0	2	2	0	1	1	0	0
<i>Microporella sarasotaensis</i>	5	0	2	1	1	1	1	0	3	3	1	0				
<i>Microporella tamiamiensis</i>	3	6	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	0
<i>Oncousoecia</i> sp.	0	1	0	0												
<i>Plesioleidochasma</i> cf. <i>vestitum</i>	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0								
<i>Pourtalesella chiarae</i>	9	5	0	0	0	3	1	0	0	8	0	0	0	1	0	0
<i>Puellina scripta</i>	3	7	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	0	0
<i>Reptadeonella umbilicata</i>	1	1	0	0												
<i>Stylopoma leverhulme</i>	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	0								
<i>Trypostega composita</i>	0	3	0	0												

Abbreviations: L, losses; R, reciprocal overgrowth; SO, stand-offs; W, wins. Grey boxes indicate that no interactions were observed with the named group.

edge to growing edge, while in flank and rear encounters occurs growing edge to non-growing edge.

To explore whether the number of intra- and inter-specific interactions observed differs from a null expectation, colonies were randomly picked without replacement from all the observations to create new pairs, and the number of intra- and interspecific interactions is re-tabulated. This randomization was repeated 1000 times to produce a null expectation to which our observations were compared. To explore whether a given taxon is a winner or loser, wins were modelled as binomial probabilities to obtain uncertainty estimates. To explore what combination of variables, including relative zooid size and

multilayered growth, best predict overgrowth outcomes (win, draw, i.e. reciprocal or stand-off, or lose), an ordinal regression analysis was performed using a cumulative logit model (see Liow *et al.* 2019 for details) implemented in the *clm* package (Christensen 2019). We used Akaike's information criteria (AIC) as the model selection criterion. All statistical analyses were conducted in R version 3.6.1 (R Core Team 2019). All datasets and R scripts necessary to reproduce the analyses are available in the Supplementary Materials and from the corresponding author upon request. All figured specimens are registered in the paleontological collections of the Invertebrate Paleontology Division, Florida Museum of Natural History, University of Florida (acronym UF).

Fig. 3. An *Anomia* shell encrusted by bryozoan colonies competing for space (Shell 3, UF 305779). The SEM micrographs are the close-up of the area outlined in the black rectangle. Last panel on the right shows the outline of seven colonies competing for space: A, F and G, *Microporella sarasotaensis*; B, *Pourtalesella chiarae*; C and E, *Puellina scripta*; and D, *Metroperiella reversa*. A overgrows G; B overgrows A; C overgrows E; D overgrows C, E and G; and F overgrows E. Solid grey indicates empty substrate space. [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

Table 2. Summary of the composition of the bryozoan palaeo-community. For each category, the total number (no.All) of the entities in the rows and the number of those involved in competitive interactions (no.Int) are reported.

	no.All	no.Int
Genera	26	24
Species	29	26
Cyclostomes	1	1
Cheilostomes	28	25
Anasca	9	6
Ascophora	19	19
Colonies	5766	—

Results

Anomia simplex shells as a substratum

We studied 867 left valves of the bivalve *Anomia simplex* encrusted by bryozoans. As opposed to the right valves of *Anomia* which are flat to slightly concave to fit the hard substratum to which they attach, left valves are convex and movable, making them a common component of the lower Tamiami shell deposits. Valve shape varies from sub-circular to sub-oval in plan view, and valves reach up to 3–4 cm in length. The outer surface was encrusted in 831 shells (96%), while the inner surface was encrusted in 535 shells (62%), and obliterated by cemented sediment, which prevented any further observations, in 195 shells

(22%). Shell areal coverage is variable, usually 5–30%, reaching 50–60% in some shells; rarely, shells are completely enveloped. Bryozoans are the most abundant epibionts, with a total of 5766 colonies, 3172 colonies (55%) located on the outer surfaces and 2594 colonies (45%) on the inner surfaces. Each shell hosts 1 to 51 bryozoan colonies (mean 6.65; median 5), with colonies sometimes extending from one surface to the other. The bryozoan assemblage is relatively low in diversity, comprising 29 species in 26 genera and 22 families, and including a single cyclostome and 28 cheilostomes (9 anascan- and 19 ascophoran-grade) (Di Martino *et al.* 2019). Other epibionts present on the shells, but strongly subordinate, at least in part due to our selective collecting in favour of bryozoans, include barnacles, the coral *Astrangia*, an encrusting foraminiferan ascribable to the genus *Planorbulina*, and spirorbid polychaetes. Ctenostome bryozoan borings ascribable to the genus *Spathipora* have also been observed on some shells.

Interactions between bryozoans and other organisms

A limited number of interactions (158) were observed between bryozoans and other epibionts including barnacles (81), the coral *Astrangia* (37), encrusting foraminifera of the genus *Planorbulina* (30), and spirorbid polychaetes (10). The majority are win-lose overgrowths (142), in which the

Table 3. For all the bryozoan species observed in the palaeocommunity, summary of the number of colonies (no.Col), dominance (D in %), interactions played (Int), number of species with which they interact excluding themselves (Spp.Int), and presence (Y) absence (N) of intraspecific interactions (Intra.Int). * indicates species that are still extant today. Colonies of Cheilostome indet. are reported here for completeness; however, these data were excluded from taxon counts and analysis.

Species	no.Col	D (%)	Int	Spp.Int	Intra.Int
<i>Acanthodesia</i> cf. <i>denticulata</i> *	1	0.02	0	–	–
<i>Acanthodesia</i> sp.	11	0.19	6	2	Y
<i>Amphiblestrum constrictum</i>	109	1.89	63	14	Y
<i>Aplosina grandis</i>	165	2.86	183	19	Y
<i>Cauloramphus</i> sp.	3	0.05	0	–	–
<i>Celleporaria</i> sp.	24	0.42	10	4	N
<i>Copidozoum</i> cf. <i>parvirostris</i>	8	0.14	5	4	N
<i>Cyclocolpota perforata</i>	247	4.28	114	12	Y
<i>Cycloperiella rubra</i>	94	1.63	67	14	Y
<i>Floridina regularis</i>	554	9.60	359	18	Y
<i>Hippaliosina rostrigera</i> *	7	0.12	5	4	N
<i>Hippopleurifera mucronata</i> *	51	0.88	27	10	N
<i>Metropieriella reversa</i>	190	3.30	116	14	Y
<i>Micropora stellata</i>	9	0.16	4	3	N
<i>Microporella</i> cf. <i>pontifica</i> *	1364	23.66	401	20	Y
<i>Microporella sarasotaensis</i>	592	10.27	370	16	Y
<i>Microporella tamiamiensis</i>	446	7.73	184	14	Y
<i>Oncousoecia</i> sp.	9	0.16	1	1	N
<i>Osburnea</i> aff. <i>biscuta</i> *	3	0.05	0	–	–
<i>Plesioleidochasma</i> cf. <i>vestitum</i>	106	1.84	40	11	N
<i>Pourtalesella chiarae</i>	510	8.84	255	19	Y
<i>Puellina scripta</i> *	917	15.90	468	19	Y
<i>Reptadeonella umbilicata</i>	109	1.89	70	15	N
<i>Smittoidea maleposita</i>	25	0.43	11	5	N
<i>Spiniflabellum laurae</i>	2	0.03	2	2	N
<i>Stephanollina vorax</i>	78	1.35	25	10	N
<i>Stylopoma leverhulmei</i>	13	0.23	2	2	N
<i>Trypostega composita</i>	97	1.68	84	11	Y
<i>Watersipora</i> sp.	9	0.16	3	2	N
Cheilostome indet.	13	0.23	1	1	N

bryozoan wins in 82 (52%) and loses in 60 (38%) encounters, followed by stand-offs (15; 9%), and a single reciprocal overgrowth. Eighteen bryozoan species have encounters with barnacles, 76 are win–lose overgrowths with the bryozoan winning in 46 (57%) and losing in 30 (37%) encounters, only 4 (5%) are stand-offs, and one is a reciprocal overgrowth. Thirteen bryozoan species encounter the coral *Astrangia*, 33 are win–lose overgrowths in which the bryozoan wins 22 (59%) times and loses 11 (30%) encounters,

and 4 (11%) are stand-offs. Nine bryozoan species interact with the encrusting foraminifera *Planorbulina*, 24 are win–lose overgrowths with the bryozoan winning in 7 (23%) and losing in 17 (57%) encounters, and 6 (20%) are stand-offs. Six bryozoan species interact with spirorbids, with the bryozoan winning in 7 (70%) encounters, losing in 2 (20%), and stand-off in one (10%). Table 1 summarizes the competitive outcomes between each bryozoan species and the different groups of organisms.

Interactions among bryozoan colonies

Twenty-six out of 29 bryozoan species in this palaeocommunity are observed to have interacted, comprising one cyclostome and 25 cheilostomes (6 anascan- and 19 ascophoran-grade) (Table 2). The three species not observed interacting are very rare, each represented by only one to three colonies in our samples. Figure 4A shows the proportions of win–lose overgrowths (W/L), stand-offs (SO), reciprocal overgrowths (R) and fouling (F) among the 1438 observed interactions between bryozoan colonies. The majority of interactions are win–lose overgrowths (c. 60%), followed by stand-offs (c. 40%), while reciprocal overgrowths and fouling are negligible. Interspecific encounters (between different species) account for the 76% of the total, with win–lose overgrowths more common than stand-offs (Fig. 4B). Conversely, stand-offs are more common than win–lose overgrowths in intraspecific encounters (between the same species), representing the remaining 24% of encounters (Fig. 4C). For all species in our dataset with at least 25 interactions, we compared the number of intra- and interspecific interactions observed and the null distribution generated from 1000 randomized datasets (Fig. 5). For most of the species, the observed number of interactions does not overlap the null distribution; that is, they participate in more intraspecific interactions and fewer interspecific interactions than expected. Tables 3 and 4 summarize all the interaction data available for each species.

In 81 of the 232 intraspecific stand-offs (35%), we observed apparent fusion of the two colonies involved (Fig. 6). Here, the contact between the two colonies is marked by single or multiple rows of irregularly shaped, variably sized kenozooids which are only found at the stand-off edge, while autozooids are deflected laterally from this point, such that the two colonies continue to grow side by side. Stand-offs with ‘fusion’ involved nine species, both anascan- and ascophoran-grade, but were more common in anascans (see Table 4).

Table 4. Summary of the different competitive outcomes for each species in the palaeocommunity involved in at least one interaction.

Species	W	L	R	SO	F	aF	WL. prop	Intra.SO. prop	Intra.SO. 'fusion' prop
<i>Acanthodesia</i> sp.	2	0	0	4	0	0	1.00	1.00	0.50
<i>Amphiblestrum constrictum</i>	15	26	2	19	1	0	0.37	0.11	0.00
<i>Aplousina grandis</i>	94	18	0	71	0	0	0.84	0.42	0.50
<i>Celleporaria</i> sp.	6	1	0	3	0	0	0.86	0.00	0.00
<i>Copidozoum</i> cf. <i>parvirostris</i>	0	2	0	3	0	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
<i>Cyclocolposa perforata</i>	40	24	3	46	1	0	0.63	0.39	0.28
<i>Cycloperiella rubra</i>	37	17	0	11	0	2	0.69	0.18	0.00
<i>Floridina regularis</i>	110	96	6	143	1	3	0.53	0.49	0.46
<i>Hippaliosina rostrigera</i> *	4	0	0	1	0	0	1.00	0.00	0.00
<i>Hippopleurifera mucronata</i> *	13	7	1	5	1	0	0.65	0.00	0.00
<i>Metropieriella reversa</i>	58	13	2	40	1	2	0.82	0.65	0.27
<i>Micropora stellata</i>	2	1	0	1	0	0	0.67	0.00	0.00
<i>Microporella</i> cf. <i>pontifica</i> *	49	145	2	197	6	2	0.25	0.61	0.07
<i>Microporella sarasotaensis</i>	124	103	3	135	2	3	0.55	0.64	0.12
<i>Microporella tamiamiensis</i>	48	70	1	61	2	2	0.41	0.46	0.04
<i>Oncousoecia</i> sp.	0	0	0	1	0	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
<i>Plesioleidochasma</i> cf. <i>vestitum</i>	7	21	0	11	1	0	0.25	0.00	0.00
<i>Pourtalesella chiarae</i>	91	83	10	64	2	5	0.52	0.28	0.05
<i>Puellina scripta</i> *	101	190	5	165	4	3	0.35	0.33	0.00
<i>Reptadeonella umbilicata</i>	36	7	2	25	0	0	0.84	0.00	0.00
<i>Smittoidea maleposita</i>	5	0	0	6	0	0	1.00	0.00	0.00
<i>Spiniflabellum laurae</i>	0	1	0	1	0	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
<i>Stephanollina vorax</i>	2	16	0	7	0	0	0.11	0.00	0.00
<i>Stylopoma leverhulme</i>	2	0	0	0	0	0	1.00	–	0.00
<i>Trypostega composita</i>	12	20	1	23	14	14	0.38	0.26	0.00
<i>Watersipora</i> sp.	2	0	0	1	0	0	1.00	0.00	0.00
Cheilostome indet.	1	0	0	0	0	0	1.00	–	0.00

Abbreviations: aF, fouled; F, fouling; Intra.SO 'fusion' prop, proportions of intraspecific stand-offs resulting in a 'fusion' between the two colonies involved; Intra.SO.prop, proportions of intraspecific stand-offs out of the total stand-offs; L lost; SO, stand-off; W, won; WL.prop, proportions of overgrowths won out of the total win–lose overgrowths.

Winner and loser species

Figure 7 shows the binomial probability of winning for all species involved in at least 25 interspecific win–lose overgrowth interactions. *Aplousina grandis*, *Metropieriella reversa*, *Reptadeonella umbilicata* and *Cycloperiella rubra* have winning probabilities greater than 0.5, while *Puellina scripta*, *Microporella tamiamiensis*, *M. cf. pontifica*, *Plesioleidochasma cf. vestitum* and *Stephanollina vorax* are losers. The remaining species (*Microporella sarasotaensis*, *Floridina regularis*, *Pourtalesella chiarae*, *Cyclocolposa perforata*, *Trypostega composita*, *Amphiblestrum constrictum* and *Hippopleurifera mucronata*) have binomial confidence intervals that cross the 0.5 line, hovering around the expected probability given no particular competitive edge or disadvantage. The binomial probability of winning and the total number of colonies observed, taken as an estimate of species relative to abundance/ecological commonness, are negatively correlated ($r = -0.35$, 95% CI = $-0.7205907-0.1764535$, $P = 0.184$; Fig. 8), showing that the best competitors for substrate space are never very common (e.g. *Aplousina grandis* and *Reptadeonella umbilicata*), while some poor competitors (e.g. *Puellina scripta* and *Microporella tamiamiensis*) are the most common species in the palaeocommunity.

Do relative zooid size, multilayered colony growth and encounter angle predict overgrowth outcomes?

Our models (Table 5) confirm that a larger relative zooid size and multilayered colony growth are both factors contributing to winning overgrowth encounters (Table 6). Figure 9 (in blue) shows the effect of the encounter angle (rear and flank) on the binomial probability of winning, given that the interaction is a win. For five of seven species whose win probabilities are <0.5, coming from the flank or rear improved the chances of winning beyond the toss of a coin at 0.5. For six, the probability of flank/rear attack in a win outcome is higher than the probability of winning. Even for the 'winners', the probability of winning an encounter coming from the flank or rear is over 0.5 for five out of nine species.

Discussion and conclusions

This study focuses on overgrowth competition among bryozoan species encrusting nearly 3-million-year-old shells of the bivalve *Anomia simplex*. The taxonomic baseline for this analysis was established in a previous study (Di Martino et al. 2019), allowing

Fig. 4. Histograms showing the proportions of the different types of interactions in our dataset. Abbreviations: WL, win–lose overgrowths; SO, stand-offs; R, reciprocal overgrowths; F, fouling. A, all 1438 interactions in the dataset (interspecific and intraspecific). B, interspecific interactions only (tot. 1090). C, intraspecific interactions only (tot. 348). Numbers above each column indicate the total number of interactions observed for each type (see Table 4 for species-level details).

the species-level identification of almost all bryozoan colonies present in the assemblage (see Table 3). Among the potential hard substrates present in Units 10/11 of the lower Tamiami Formation, the left valves of *A. simplex* appear to be the most frequently colonized by epibionts, especially bryozoans (our target). It is likely that shell colonization happened post-mortem, owing to the high proportion of shells encrusted on inner surfaces. Although the bryozoan assemblage found on the shells consists of 29 species, only six are dominant. These are each represented by more than 400 colonies, accounting for 76% of total bryozoan abundance. Subordinately, other epibionts were found to occur haphazardly on the shells, including barnacles, corals, encrusting foraminifera and spirorbids (Fig. 2). Although the proportion of the shell surface area encrusted is generally low, with plenty of substrate space unoccupied, this is often the case for bryozoan communities (e.g. Rosso & Sanfilippo 2005; Taylor *et al.* 2019) and does not preclude competition for space between bryozoan colonies and other epibionts that happen to grow close to one

Fig. 5. Comparing intra- and interspecific interactions to null distributions. Plot (for species with at least 25 interactions observed) of the number of intra- and interspecific interactions observed, and the median and the full range of observed outcomes of the dataset resampled 1000 times, with respect to interacting partners (circles). Note that for many of the data-rich species, the observation (triangles) does not overlap the null distribution (circles), implying that there are more intraspecific interactions and fewer interspecific interactions than expected. [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

another. A limited number of interactions has been observed among non-bryozoan epibionts and bryozoan colonies. Bryozoans win the majority of these encounters and are thus seemingly more successful in competitive overgrowth than other taxonomic groups except for encrusting foraminifera which win more often than bryozoans. Although competitive interactions involving encrusting foraminifera are generally rare, encrusting agglutinated foraminifera from the subfamily Rhabdammininae and the family Ammodiscidae were also observed to be the main competitor with bryozoans for substrate space on Miocene plate corals from East Kalimantan (Di Martino *et al.* 2015). Likewise, in modern shallow, shelf environments of Bahamas, encrusting foraminifera are significantly more likely to overgrow multicellular organisms, such as bryozoans, than to be overgrown by them (Richardson-White & Walker 2011).

Based on the outcome of bryozoan win–lose overgrowth interactions in our system, we were able to distinguish bryozoan species that are winners and others that are losers (Fig. 7). We found that ecological abundance (number of colonies observed) is

Fig. 6. Examples of stand-offs with ‘fusion’ in two anascan-grade bryozoan species in which it is commoner. A, three colonies of *Floridina regularis* (Shell 22, UF 305771); B, two colonies of *Aplousina grandis* (Shell 504, UF 305766). The rows of kenozooids marking the contact among colonies are shaded grey.

Fig. 7. Binomial probabilities of winning. We here plot binomial probabilities (and the 95% CI) of winning for the subset of WL data for species with 25 or more interactions observed. Top number shows the total number of interactions (including SO and R) while bottom number shows the number of colonies (regardless of whether interacting). Species for which their 95% CI falls below the null expectation of 0.5 are losers, while species for which their 95% CI falls above the null expectation of 0.5 are winners. [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

negatively correlated with the probability of a species winning (Fig. 8). Indeed, three of the five species identified as losers – *Puellina scripta*, *Microporella cf. pontifica* and *M. tamiamiensis* – dominate the assemblage (see Table 3), while none of the four species identified as winners were very abundant (Fig. 7). A negative relationship between ‘commonness’ and success in overgrowth competition was previously observed in both living (Centurión & López Gappa 2011) and fossil (Liow et al. 2019) bryozoan

Fig. 8. Correlation between the binomial probability of winning and the total number of colonies observed for species with 25 or more interactions observed. [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

Table 5. Ordinal regression models of competitive outcomes. We show results of model comparisons among four models including relative zooid size (Size) or/and multilayered growth (ML) and the null model. The best model is one that involves an interaction between size and multilayered growth.

Models	AIC	ΔAIC	df	weight
Outcome ~ NULL	2902.28	177.1	2	<0.001
Outcome ~ Size	2745.33	20.2	3	<0.001
Outcome ~ Size + ML	2727.48	2.3	5	0.24
Outcome ~ ML	2873.81	148.6	3	<0.001
Outcome ~ Size x ML	2725.18	0	7	0.76

communities. Being a relatively poor competitor but abundant is a characteristic of early colonizers, as observed for example in *Fenestulina rugula*, a pioneer species and major component of a Recent fauna

Table 6. Comparison between the estimates of the explanatory variables for our two best models involving both zooid size and multilayered growth.

Variables	Outcome ~ Size + ML		Outcome ~ Size × ML	
	Estimate	SE	Estimate	SE
Relative.zooid.size	0.778***	0.066	0.782***	0.066
Multilayered.growth	1.205***	0.283	1.122***	0.279
Relative.zooid.size*multilayered.growth	–	–	–0.630*	0.302

Abbreviation: SE, standard errors. * indicates significance at a 0.01 level and *** at >0.001.

Fig. 9. Binomial probabilities of winning given the encounter angle. We plot the binomial probability of the given species winning as a back or flank 'attacker' (triangles), given that the interaction is a win. Circles and their CIs are probabilities for the same species replotted from Figure 7 for a comparison. For six of seven species with their estimate under the null expectation (0.5 line, i.e. they have a tendency to lose), their win probability is increased if they are back or flank 'attackers' (triangles). [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

encrusting boulders in Antarctica (Barnes & Clarke 1998). Pioneer species are also more often involved in intraspecific interactions than better spatial competitors (Barnes & Kuklinski 2005). In our system, we generally observed more intraspecific interactions than expected (Fig. 5), implying clustering of conspecifics, but this is especially true for two of the above-mentioned species (*Microporella cf. pontifica* and *M. tamiamiensis*), which may have had the role of early colonizers.

For several intraspecific encounters, we also observed apparent fusion between colonies recognizable because the contact is marked by rows of kenozooids in each colony. Tissue fusion between colonies of the same species is known as homosyndrome (Knight-Jones & Moyses 1961). However, because

fossil colonies lack soft tissues, we here avoid the use of this very particular term. Fusion has been observed in living and fossil species of both cyclostome (e.g. Harmelin 1976; Rosso & Sanfilippo 2005) and cheilostome (e.g. López Gappa 1989; Barnes & Clarke 1998; Barnes & Kuklinski 2005) bryozoans. In our palaeocommunity, apparent fusion was the outcome of 4–50% of intraspecific encounters for nine different species of anascan- and ascophoran-grade cheilostomes. These proportions are much higher than the 6–10% observed in Antarctic communities (Barnes & Kuklinski 2005). For these Antarctic communities, it was observed that (1) the frequency of fusion differs significantly depending on the identity of the competitor; and (2) fusion occurs only in poor competitors in which intraspecific encounters become constructive rather than competitive (Barnes & Kuklinski 2005). Based on our system, we can confirm that the frequency of apparent fusion differs significantly depending on the species (see Table 3), but among those species involved there are losers, such as *Microporella cf. pontifica* (apparent fusion – a.f. – in eight out of 120 encounters (e.); 7%); winners, such as *Aplousina grandis* (a.f. in 15 out of 30 e.; 50%); and species with intermediate abilities, such as *Floridina regularis* (a.f. in 32 out of 70 e.; 46%) (see Fig. 7). We also observe that fusion frequency is higher in those species that are better competitors, although some of our observations may not correspond to true homosyndrome but colonies that simply abut and continue to grow side by side. On the other hand, because only closely, genetically related colonies are likely to fuse, differences in rates of apparent fusion may reflect the different dispersal potential of species, as is the case for homosyndrome rates (Barnes & Kuklinski 2005). In our system, we also observed that apparent fusion is more likely to happen in anascan-grade than in ascophoran-grade species.

Our interaction data from the Florida Pliocene corroborate previous findings from Pleistocene encrusting bryozoans in New Zealand that traits such as a larger zooid size, and to a lesser extent multilayered growth, facilitate success in competition for substrate living space (Liow *et al.* 2017,

2019). Studies on modern bryozoan communities also suggest an encounter angle effect on overgrowth outcomes, with some species faring better in frontal encounters than others, suggesting that encounter angle may be responsible for some of the variations in outcomes of pairwise overgrowth interactions (Jackson 1979; Turner & Todd 1994). Our data show quantitatively that both loser and winner species can gain an advantage when ‘attacking’ from the rear or the flank (Fig. 9).

In our dataset, only the genus *Microporella* is represented by more than one species (specifically three) involved in competitive interactions. The three species (*Microporella* cf. *pontifica*, *M. sarasotaensis* and *M. tamiamiensis*) are similar in being very common and involved in more intraspecific and fewer interspecific interactions than expected. However, while *Microporella* cf. *pontifica* and *M. tamiamiensis* were found to be losers, *M. sarasotaensis* appears to be a slightly better competitor (Fig. 7). Liow et al. (2016) found that *Microporella* as a genus is a poor proxy for individual species-specific questions on competitiveness as some species show a more stable competitive behaviour than others through time, with some individual species contributing more than others to genus competitive ability patterns.

Finally, among the six species in the palaeocommunity known to be still alive today in the western Atlantic (see Tables 3, 4), *Puellina scripta* and *Microporella* cf. *pontifica* are poor competitors but dominant, showing that spatial competitive ability does not always seem to affect long-term survival.

Acknowledgements. – We thank L.J. Cotton (University of Bristol) who helped collect the specimens and E. Henshaw, Jr. (President) of Schroeder-Manatee Ranch (SMR) Aggregates Inc., who kindly allowed access to the quarry. This research was funded by the Leverhulme Trust Research Project ‘Origin of high tropical diversity: a test using bryozoans’ (award no. RGP-2015-036 to P.D. Taylor), the Florida Museum of Natural History, Vokes and Southwest Florida Fossil Society Scholarships, and the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (grant agreement no. 724324 to L.H. Liow).

References

- Barnes, D.K.A. & Clarke, A. 1998: The ecology of an assemblage dominant: the encrusting bryozoan *Fenestulina rugula*. *Invertebrate Biology* 117, 331–340.
- Barnes, D.K.A. & Kuklinski, P. 2005: Bipolar patterns of intraspecific competition in bryozoans. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 285, 75–87.
- Centurión, R. & López Gappa, J. 2011: Bryozoan assemblages on hard substrata: species abundance distribution and competition for space. *Hydrobiologia* 658, 329–341.
- Christensen, R.H.B. 2019: ordinal - Regression Models for Ordinal Data. R package version 2019. 4–25. <http://www.cran.r-project.org/package=ordinal/>

- Di Martino, E., Taylor, P.D. & Johnson, K.G. 2015: Bryozoan diversity in the Miocene of the Kutai Basin, East Kalimantan, Indonesia. *Palaios* 30, 109–115.
- Di Martino, E., Taylor, P.D. & Portell, R.W. 2019: *Anomia*-associated bryozoans from the upper Pliocene (Piacenzian) lower Tamiami Formation of Florida, USA. *Palaeontologia Electronica* 22, 22.1.11.
- Harmelin, J.-G. 1976: Le sous-ordre des Tubuliporina (Bryozoaires Cyclostomes) en Méditerranée. *Ecologie et systématique. Mémoires de l’Institut Océanographique* 10, 1–326.
- Jackson, J.B.C. 1979: Overgrowth competition between encrusting cheilostome ectoprocts in a Jamaican cryptic reef environment. *Journal of Animal Ecology* 48, 805–823.
- Jones, D.S., MacFadden, B.J., Webb, S.D., Mueller, P.A., Hodell, D.A. & Cronin, T.M. 1991: Integrated geochronology of a classic Pliocene fossil site in Florida: linking marine and terrestrial biochronologies. *The Journal of Geology* 99, 637–648.
- Knight-Jones, E.W. & Moyses, J. 1961: Intraspecific competition in sedentary marine animals. *Symposia of the Society for Experimental Biology* 15, 72–95.
- Liow, L.H., Di Martino, E., Voje, K.L., Rust, S. & Taylor, P.D. 2016: Interspecific interactions through 2 million years: are competitive outcomes predictable? *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 283, 20160981.
- Liow, L.H., Di Martino, E., Krzeminska, M., Ramsfjell, M., Rust, S., Taylor, P.D. & Voje, K.L. 2017: Relative size predicts competitive outcome through 2 million years. *Ecology Letters* 20, 981–988.
- Liow, L.H., Reitan, T., Voje, K.L., Taylor, P.D. & Di Martino, E. 2019: Size, weapons, and armor as predictors of competitive outcomes in fossil and contemporary marine communities. *Ecological Monographs* 89, e01354.
- López Gappa, J. 1989: Overgrowth competition in an assemblage of encrusting bryozoans settled on artificial substrata. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 51, 121–130.
- R Core Team. 2019: *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <https://www.R-project.org/>
- Richardson-White, S. & Walker, S.E. 2011: Diversity, taphonomy and behavior of encrusting foraminifera on experimental shells deployed along a shelf-to-slope bathymetric gradient, Lee Stocking Island, Bahamas. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 312, 305–324.
- Rosso, A. & Sanfilippo, R. 2005: Bryozoans and serpuloides in skeleton communities from the Pleistocene of Sicily: spatial utilisation and competitive interactions. *Annali dell’Università di Ferrara, Museologia Scientifica e Naturalistica volume speciale* 2005, 115–130.
- Taylor, P.D. 2016: Competition between encrusters on marine hard substrates and its fossil record. *Palaeontology* 59, 481–497.
- Taylor, P.D., Di Martino, E. & Martha, S.O. 2019: Colony growth strategies, dormancy and repair in some Late Cretaceous bryozoans: insights into the ecology of the Chalk seabed. *Palaeobiodiversity and Palaeoenvironments* 99, 425–446.
- Turner, S.J. & Todd, C.D. 1994: Competition for space in encrusting bryozoan assemblages: the influence of encounter angle, site and year. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom* 74, 603–622.

Supporting Information

Additional supporting information may be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of the article.

Appendix S1. Datasets.